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Evolutionary Trends of Global Engineering Education Policy and Its Enlightenment: 2000-2017

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ABSTRACT

In order to cope with the new characteristics of the new industrial revolution industry and the new talent demand, it is essential to analyze the characteristics and trends of global engineering education policy evolution and to innovate the engineering talent training model. This paper selects 51 typical engineering education policies of the US, Germany, China, Russia, and Japan from 2000 to 2017, uses content analysis method, determines key words based on the contents of various policies and their changes, and analyzes the themes of major industrial countries' engineering education policies. Based on the frequency and changes of words, the common characteristics and evolution trends of global engineering education policies are summarized. The research finds that: (1) the US values STEM education and cultivates new engineers with computing power; (2) Germany leads the reform in engineering education through digitalization and intelligence; (3) China emphasizes the cultivation of diversified, innovative and entrepreneurial Engineers; (4) Russia focuses on engineering practice and promotes the transformation of the engineering talent system in response to industrial demand; (5) Japan is driven by innovation strategy and is committed to developing a composite engineer to solve social challenges. Based on this, we try to build a new generation of engineer capability model and put forward some countermeasures.

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INTRODUCTION

The new industrial revolution takes place under the combined effects of the technological revolution, the energy revolution, and the communications revolution. It will have a far-reaching impact on the existing technology paradigm, manufacturing methods, industrial forms, organizational forms, and business models. In the wave of the new industrial revolution, a large number of smart industries, intelligent equipment, and intelligent products with clear signs of information age have emerged. The new industrial system led by information and intelligence will be the new industrial form. Engineering education is an important part of higher education and plays a very important role in promoting the development of national science and technology. Engineering education provides a steady stream of emerging forces for the country's engineering and industrial sectors by cultivating trained laborers and innovative engineers. Since the new industrial revolution, in response to new industrial characteristics and new requirements for talents, major industrial countries in the world have issued a series of important engineering education policy plans and research reports to promote the reform of engineering education and cultivate a new generation of engineers.

International engineering education is dominated by two types of countries[1]. One category is industrial powers that have solid foundations in industry. Such countries are at the helm of the development direction of engineering education. Their development is the frontier of engineering education. The United States, Germany, and Japan are such categories. The other category is the emerging industrial powers. Such countries have unique advantages in scale and a solid personnel training system. They want to take advantage of the new industrial revolution to seize manufacturing advantages and develop new industries. Russia and China are representatives of such countries. Extracting the characteristics of engineering education policies in two types of countries is crucial for judging the state of engineering education in the global countries.

This research uses content analysis method to analyze 51 engineering education policies in the United States, Germany, Japan, Russia, and China since the 21st century, and summarizes the characteristics of engineering education policies in major industrial countries. On this basis, the global engineering education is summarized. Policy evolution trends, and finally build a new generation of engineer models based on policy trends. The evolving trend of education policy, and finally building a new generation of engineer models based on policy trends.

1 RESEARCH QUESTION

The purpose of engineering education policy is to serve the training of engineering science and technology personnel. This study aims to analyze the global engineering education policy since the 21st century and summarize the characteristics of global engineering education talents. Specifically, the research questions of this study are:

1. What are the themes of global engineering education policy focusing on talent training?
2. What are the characteristics of engineering science and technology personnel training in major industrial countries in the world?
3. What kind of enlightenment has been brought to us by the evolutionary trend of global engineering education policies?

2 METHODOLOGY

The essence of the content analysis method is to convert documents expressed in language rather than quantity into data expressed by numbers by identifying the key features in the target text, and describe the results of the analysis using statistical data, based on further "quantity" of the content of the text[2]. To identify features that can reflect certain essential aspects of the content of the literature and are easy to count, Clarify its laws and conduct Inspection and interpretation. In order to reduce the subjective bias of coders and influence the research results, the classification and coding rules in the identification analysis framework need to be verified through reliability tests to ensure the scientificity of the analysis process and results. Therefore, we need to choose different appraisers to compare the coding results of the same analysis sample, and the consistency between the two coefficients is >0.8 . [3]The reliability test results of this paper reach $\alpha = 0.9$, which proves that the classification and coding rules are scientific and reliable.

3 PROCEDURE

This study uses the content analysis model of Chou and Chang's (2010) and the study is divided into 4 steps [4]:

1.Sampling (content selection): The study focused on the engineering education policies of the United States, Germany, Japan, Russia, and China. The target policy is an important policy plan and research report issued by the Ministry of Education, the Academy of Engineering, and related departments. Through the direct search of the official website of the above-mentioned departments, the Key words such as "engineering education", "engineering talents", "sci-tech talents, and "engineers", backtracking related documents, policy planning, and retrieval of publicly issued policy texts and research reports.In order to ensure the accuracy and representativeness of the policy text, the policy of closely related to the main content engineering education (The engineering education policy must be the subject of a report or a chapter, otherwise it will not be collected.) . In the end, 51 typical policy documents at the national level were categorized from three aspects: the introduction of time, the introduction of institutions, and the policy name. (Appendix 2).

2. Conceptualization: Corresponding to the issues raised previously, this study focuses on the following three aspects: (a) Global Engineering Education Policy Focuses on Topics, (b) Characteristics of Engineering Education Policy in Major Industrial Countries, (c) Global engineering education policy evolution trends.

3. Operationalization (Variable identification): Based on research issues, a code book for inductive coding strategies was created.

4. Coding Verification (Confidence Check): This study uses the triangulation method[5] of Miles and Huberman (1984) to obtain research data from multiple sources of information such as the official website of the Ministry of Education, the Academy of Engineering report, and the website of the Industry and Information Commission. At the same time, during the coding process, more than two doctoral students jointly handle the selected policies and reports. Subsequently, the completed code is submitted to a highly experienced professor of engineering education.

3.1 CODING BOOK

The coding manual, as a research guide, describes the classification principles of the first three research questions. The policy texts and reports collected will be systematically processed in accordance with these principles.[6] In the above, the key words for the training of engineering talents are: A-emphasis on multidisciplinary integration, B- highlighting engineering practice, C-cultivating engineering innovation ability, D-oriented industry demand, E- focused STEM education, F-STEM education, G- Engineering ethics. In coding, the policy coding range is from 1-51, and the global engineering education policy focuses on A-G changes.

3.2 Engineering education personnel training

Table 1 summarizes the operation description of the text encoding classification.

Table 1. Coding Strategies for Engineering Talent Cultivation

Coding	Category	Description
A	Multidisciplinary integration	Cross-convergence requirements in various fields, reviewing and solving problems from an overall macro perspective.
B	Engineering practice ability	With engineering professional skills, knowledge application capabilities and engineering conception.
C	Engineering innovation and entrepreneurship	With innovative engineering thinking, he has the intention and ability to engage in entrepreneurial activities in related fields such as engineering, technology development, production and service.
D	For industry needs	The skills possessed by engineering graduates match the needs of the industry and can meet the needs of the society and promote the development of the industry.

E	STEM education	STEM education relies on project practice and real situations to cultivate students' ability to solve problems using the four aspects of science, technology, mathematics, and engineering, and cultivate students' cross-knowledge structure. The coding needs to explicitly mention STEM education and be separated from the discipline.
F	Respond to social challenges	Cultivate new engineers who can solve the economic and social problems facing society in this century.
G	Engineering ethics	Establish the concept of symbiotic development of industrial development and eco-environment, the concept of integration of professional ethics and engineering practice.

3.3 Text frequency statistics

On the basis of collecting and arranging related policies, 51 policy texts are coded according to "text numbering - specific clauses/chapter". If there is a case where policy texts contain policy tools for comprehensive use, serial numbers are assigned sequentially according to the contents of the extracted policies, and a form of "text preparation—specific terms/chapter-serial numbers" is formed, and finally a coding table of policy content analysis units is formed. Based on the frequency and proportion of the seven keywords in five major industrial countries, draw a two-dimensional map of policy texts (Figure 1).

G	1-6; 6; 12	21-3;	37-2		
F	10;10-3	18-3;	30-4;37-4;32-1;25-1;26-3	40-3	
E	2-3;4;11-6;10-1		38-3		
D	7-3;8-4	13;14-1; 15-2;18-2;19-5;21-1	22-3;28-3-2;29-4;36;37	40-4;41-1;43-1;43-2	48-2;49-2-1;50-3-3;51-2-5;52-3;53-1;54-4
C	2-2;6-4;7;8;9-3	15-1;18;19-3;20;21-2	23-2;24-1;26-2;27-7;28-3-4;29-3;31-3;34-4;35-4	42-3;44;45;46-3	49-1-3;51-2-8;53-3
B	5;11-3;10-1	17	31-1;34-2	40-2;41-2;42-1;43-3;45-3	49-2-2;50-3-4;51-2-7;54-3
A	1-3;2-1;8-3;9-1;10	21-5;14-2;16	36-2;38-2	42-2;43-2	49-1-2;50-3-5;51-2-6;52-2
	United States	Germany	Japan	Russia	China

Figure 1 Two-dimensional distribution of policy texts

4 FINDINGS

4.1 Analysis of policy texts

Since the 21st century, the number of global engineering education policies has steadily increased. Especially since 2008, engineering education policies have exploded, and engineering education has become an important part of higher education. This study collected 51 engineering education policies from 2000 to 2017, including 12 US engineering education policies, 9 in Germany, 16 in Japan, 8 in Russia, and 6 in China. Among the 51 engineering education policies, the keywords “for industry demand (D)” and “engineering innovation and entrepreneurship” (C) accounted for nearly half of the total, indicating that major industrial countries pay particular attention to cultivating innovative engineering talents for industrial needs. “Multidisciplinary integration” (A) and “Engineering practice ability” (B) accounted for 15.84% and 14.85%, respectively, reaching an average of the proportion, indicating that countries are paying more attention to interdisciplinary and engineering practice when cultivating engineering talents. In addition, “STEM education” (E) accounted for 6.93%, “respond to social challenges” (F) accounted for 8.91%, and “engineering ethics” (G) accounted for 4.95%. Among them, STEM education became a hot spot in American engineering education policy, responding to social challenges. To become the focus of Japan's engineering education policy formulation, Germany and the United States are also increasingly concerned about engineering ethics.

4.2 Characteristics of evolutionary trends in major industrial countries

The core elements of national engineering education policy texts can be extracted from Figure 1:

1. The United States: Emphasizing STEM Education, Training Innovative Engineers with Cross-knowledge Background

From the data point of view, STEM education and multidisciplinary integration accounted for the highest proportion of engineering education policies in the United States (all accounted for 4.95%, followed by engineering innovation and entrepreneurship (3.96%), engineering ethics (2.97%), engineering practice ability (2.97%), for industry demand (1.98%), and response to social challenges (1.98%). In general, the U.S. engineering education policy has the following characteristics: (1) Emphasizing STEM education, attempting to build a large system of engineering education based on the learning of interdisciplinary projects; (2) Advance design, dedicated to training future-oriented engineers and technology talents. Propose the "2020 Engineers Plan" report, and on this basis, formulate action plans for innovative engineering talents; (3) Strengthen the intersection of disciplines and explore the multiple modes and innovative approaches for engineering talent training; (4) Emphasis on engineering practice requires students to connect theory with practice.

2. Germany: Focusing on Industrial Needs, Emphasizing the Development of Digital and Intelligent Talents

From the data point of view, Germany pays special attention to the cultivation of industry demand and innovative engineering talents. The industry-oriented demand

(4.95%) and innovation engineering talents (5.94%) have the highest proportion of their engineering education. In the rest, multidisciplinary integration accounted for 2.97%, and engineering practice ability accounted for 0.99%. Generally speaking, the German engineering education policy has the following characteristics: (1) Transforming the engineering education system for industrial needs, and the policy is tilted towards digital and intelligent engineering talents; (2) The institutionalization of industry-university cooperation provides policy guarantees for the smooth implementation of engineering education practice. Adopt the “dual system” and “double-training” personnel training methods. Schools and enterprises jointly undertake the cultivation of talents. The school is responsible for theoretical teaching, the company is responsible for practical teaching, and improves engineering students' practical ability and innovation.

3. Japan: Driven by innovation strategy, dedicated to developing composite engineers to solve social challenges

From a data point of view, Japan placed the training of engineering talents in innovation and entrepreneurship at the top of the list, accounting for 8.91% of the total. In addition, Japan emphasized the importance of cultivating engineers who can cope with the major social challenges, the “responding to major social challenges”. accounted for 5.94%. In the rest, multidisciplinary integration accounted for 1.98%, engineering practice ability accounted for 1.98%, STEM education accounted for 0.99%, and engineering ethics accounted for 0.99%. In general, the Japanese engineering education policy has the following characteristics: (1) Actively develop innovative research and strive to cultivate composite engineers that solve social challenges; (2) Build an open and innovative talent training system and call for interaction between technological innovation and society; (3) Actively invest funds in the engineering field, focusing on Investment in engineering talents in areas such as internet of things, energy, and information technology.

4. Russia: Focus on engineering practice and promote the transformation of engineering talent system for industrial development

From the data point of view, engineering practice ability accounted for 4.95%, engineering innovation and entrepreneurship accounted for 3.96%, facing the industry demand accounted for 3.96%, multidisciplinary integration accounted for 1.98%, to deal with social challenges of 0.99%. In general, the Russian engineering education policy focuses on engineering practice for industrial needs, and its engineering education policy presents the following characteristics: (1) Legalization of internal and external cooperation mechanisms in engineering education, internal cooperation with universities and large-scale enterprises, and resource sharing measures to improve the practical ability of engineering talents; (2) Actively fostering innovative talents through universities, Science and technology parks, university business incubators and other training professionals; (3) Based on cross-disciplinary, develop comprehensive talents that meet industry needs.

5. China: Promoting the New Engineering Paradigm and Developing a New Generation of Engineers Facing Industry Needs

The development of engineering education policies in China has seen an explosive growth in the last two years. From the data point of view, the industry-oriented demand accounted for 6.93%, multidisciplinary and engineering practices ability accounted for 3.96%, and engineering innovation and entrepreneurship accounted for 2.97%. In general, China's engineering education policy has the following characteristics: (1) Cultivate diversified, innovative and entrepreneurial engineers, and implement discipline professional construction to adapt to industrial transformation and upgrading; (2) Build a new engineering talent system and implement an excellent engineer training program; (3) Promote the integration of production and education, and strengthen the transformation of scientific and technological achievements.

4.3 New Generation Engineer Model Construction based on policy trend

Through the analysis of 51 major industrial countries' engineering education policies, it can be seen that global engineering talent cultivation shows the general direction of demand practice, innovation, compound, and international vision. The topics of engineering talent training focus on: interdisciplinary integration capabilities, engineering practice capabilities, innovation and entrepreneurship capabilities, facing industry needs, addressing major social challenges, STEM education, and engineering ethics. Combining the extracted key words and the core characteristics of engineering education policies in major industrial countries, and comprehensively considering the research literature on future capability of engineering science and technology talents at home and abroad, this paper exploratorily builds a new generation of engineers' core competencies model, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 New Generation Engineer Capability Model

In the framework of a new generation of engineers' capabilities, engineers are weighted toward future-oriented core competencies such as basic skills and engineering ethics, intelligent applications, interdisciplinary collaboration, and engineering entrepreneurship. Hard skills refer to professional knowledge and

capabilities. Basic skills are equal to the sum of hard skills and soft skills such as engineering practice and communication and leadership skills. Above basic skills is the core competence for the future, which is the difference between the new generation of engineers' capability framework and the traditional engineer's capability framework. This paper will focus on the future of the core capabilities are divided into four levels, engineering ethics, intelligent application capabilities, cross-disciplinary collaboration capabilities and engineering entrepreneurial capabilities.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

By analyzing the engineering education policies of the major industrial countries in the world, it is found that countries have significant commonalities in the field of concern and the cultivation of engineering talents. The engineering education policies of various countries are obviously inclined in the cultivation of artificial intelligence, internet of things and big data engineering talents. At the same time, countries have reached a consensus on training a new generation of engineers and engineers with engineering practice capabilities, innovation and entrepreneurship capabilities, and interdisciplinary collaboration capabilities. From the perspective of policy trends, the future engineering education reforms in various countries can be broken through four aspects: (1) speeding up the integration of education and information technology; (2) Strengthening the connection between engineering talents and industrial needs; (3) training model for innovative engineers; (4) Strengthen interdisciplinary collaboration.

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